

LIFESTYLES

IN PUBLIC HEALTH, MARKETING AND PRO-ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH

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Summary

In this report we synthesise insights from 82 conceptual and empirical studies of lifestyle from four main research fields: general lifestyle studies; public health; marketing and consumer behaviour; pro-environmental behaviour and climate mitigation (termed 'low-carbon'). The first four sections cover each of these fields. The final fifth section draws out similarities, differences and lessons learnt. It concludes with some insights to strengthen future-oriented scenarios and modelling of low-carbon lifestyles.

Throughout the report, we summarise our findings in response to four main questions:

- (1) how are lifestyles and lifestyle change defined and applied?
- (2) how are lifestyles identified and measured?
- (3) how heterogeneous are lifestyles, and what lifestyles groups are commonly identified?
- (4) how is lifestyle change promoted through public policy interventions?

Details of the literature search criteria and sample characteristics are included in the Appendices, and the full annotated bibliographies are available on request.

Key Findings: Lifestyle concepts and elements

Three common elements of lifestyle are *behaviours* (which are observable), *cognitions* (which are not observable), and *contextual factors* which shape how behaviours and cognitions interact. The World Health Organisation, for example, defines lifestyle as patterns of behaviour determined by the interplay between individual characteristics, social interactions, and socioeconomic conditions. In marketing, lifestyle is viewed as a way of everyday life that leads to choices between goods, services and expenditure which reflect values, intentions and opinions. Lifestyles are evident in behavioural patterns and routines, in intentions and goals, and in the construction of self-identity and social identity.

In public health and marketing, lifestyles tend to be interpreted in a general integrative sense (we each have one lifestyle), whereas in low-carbon research lifestyles are also applied to specific domains (we each have a food lifestyle, a travel lifestyle, a domestic

lifestyle). Domain-specific lifestyles can result in inconsistencies between behaviours and cognitions in different domains, which means it is problematic to identify low-carbon lifestyles from behavioural patterns alone. Lifestyles and behaviours are also not synonymous: lifestyles are an integrative concept whereas behaviours are discrete actions. Low-carbon research in particular tends to blur this distinction by focusing on certain high or low impact behaviours and how they might be changed.

Key Findings: Application of lifestyle concepts

Lifestyle concepts are applied in research in three main ways: *descriptively*, to characterise heterogeneity and clustering of behaviours and individuals in a population; *analytically* to understand outcomes of interest; and *instrumentally* to design lifestyle-change interventions. Public health, marketing and pro-environmental research share these three applications but to different ends. In marketing, for example, *descriptive* applications of lifestyle classifications are used to segment markets and position products and services relative to specific lifestyle groups. In low-carbon research, for example, *analytical* applications are used to associate lifestyle elements or groups with high or low carbon footprints. In public health, for example, *instrumental* applications of risk factors associated with morbidity are used to design targeted interventions to alleviate disease burdens.

There are many similarities in how lifestyle is conceptualised, measured and analysed across public health, marketing and low-carbon research fields, but there are also some important differences. For example, public health and low-carbon research place more emphasis on motivated reasoning for lifestyle change and so lifestyle elements such as values, problem awareness, and self-efficacy. In contrast, marketing research places more emphasis on identity and social positioning, as well as the private benefits of lifestyle change. Public health and marketing research also tend to find or assume consistency in lifestyles whereas low-carbon research points to inconsistencies between behaviours and cognitions (e.g., knowledge-action gap, value-action gap) or inconsistencies between domains (e.g., low-carbon diet but high-carbon travel).

Key Findings: Measurement of lifestyles and lifestyle groups

Each research field has a variety of widely-used frameworks for measuring lifestyles. In public health, for example, the Health Promoting Lifestyle Profile (HPLP) framework measures individual practices associated with health, attitudes, mental resilience and social relationships. In marketing, frameworks tend to be proprietary to market research companies, but also include the VALS2 framework which measures values, interests in technology, and social character, using publicly-available data from the World Values Survey. In low-carbon research, there are no dominant frameworks as lifestyles are measured in at least five different ways, based on behavioural commitment, basic orientations, perceptions of self and world, consistency across domains, or contextual influences. Integrative frameworks recognise the entwined challenges of public health and environmental protection. For example, the Lifestyle of Health and Sustainability (LOHAS) framework identifies five dimensions of sustainable economy, health, personal development, alternative health care, and ecological lifestyles.

Data used to measure lifestyle elements in these frameworks are collected in a variety of ways, from case studies in defined contexts to nationally-representative questionnaire surveys. The large sample quantitative studies commonly use latent class, factor, or cluster analytic techniques to identify distinct lifestyle groups with similar behaviours and cognitions.

Key Findings: Lifestyle change and interventions

Lifestyle change may be motivated by intentions and a striving for self-consistency, or may be caused by a change in context. In marketing, lifestyle change is explained by shifts in the lifestyle landscape including contextual and cognitive factors that influence consumption patterns. Public policy interventions in health, environment and other fields promote or enable lifestyle change towards beneficial private and societal outcomes. Evidence from public health shows that changing lifestyle to improve health and wellbeing involves a reassessment of values, attitudes and goals, within the constraints of personal circumstances. This means lifestyle-change interventions need to (1) be tailored to specific circumstances, (2) empower individuals by reinforcing problem awareness and self-efficacy, and (3) change the wider social and physical environment to support healthy outcomes. Low-carbon interventions tend to place stronger emphasis on values and motivated action as drivers of lifestyle change, but can also abnegate individual responsibility by emphasising the need for deep and long-lasting systemic change. Low-carbon lifestyle change is therefore awkwardly positioned between behavioural change on the one hand and systemic change on the other.

Key Findings: Insights for low-carbon research and modelling

There are many useful insights from public health and marketing which can be applied to research on low-carbon lifestyles. As examples, low-carbon research could usefully: (1) identify wellbeing, social relationships, and other cognitions and contextual factors necessary to understand lifestyles; (2) draw on national panel datasets used to track healthy lifestyles or distinguish consumer-based lifestyle groups; (3) design interventions which act on behavioural, cognitive and contextual influences on lifestyle in a concerted manner.

Representing lifestyles in global modelling of low-carbon futures is a relatively new field with significant challenges. Lifestyle change to-date has been implemented as a relatively arbitrary set of behavioural changes (within existing technological and infrastructural contexts) motivated by normative awareness of climate change described in scenario narratives. These do not typically recognise lifestyle heterogeneity (within and between countries) as well as potential inconsistencies between intentions and actions. For scenario narratives as well as endogenous representations of lifestyle change, a small number of lifestyle archetypes or generalisable groups are necessary. These should be informed by analysis of historical data on consumption activity which tracks both change over time and between countries, as well as other globally generalisable lifestyle measurement frameworks.

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1 General Concepts, Definitions, and Elements of Lifestyle

Summary

This section introduces basic lifestyle concepts, their meaning, and the different perspectives taken on what constitutes a lifestyle. Three common elements of lifestyle are observable behaviours, non-observable cognitions, and contextual factors which shape how behaviours and cognitions interact. Lifestyles and behaviours are not synonymous: lifestyles are an integrative concept whereas behaviours are discrete actions. Different perspectives on lifestyle emphasise behavioural patterns, intentions and goals, or the process through which self-identity is constructed. Lifestyle change may be motivated by intentions and a striving for self-consistency, or may be caused by a change in context. Public policy interventions in health, environment and other fields promote or enable lifestyle change towards beneficial private and societal outcomes. Lifestyles concepts are used in research in three main ways: descriptively, to characterise heterogeneity and clustering of behaviours and individuals in a population; analytically to understand outcomes of interest such as morbidity or greenhouse gas emissions; and instrumentally to target differentiated interventions at specific lifestyle groups.

1.1 What does lifestyle mean? What constitutes a lifestyle?

‘Lifestyle’ means a coherent pattern of behaviours and cognitions consistent with specific contextual factors. *Behaviours* are observable and include actions, activities, technology adoption, and consumption. *Cognitions* are non-observable and include worldviews, concerns, beliefs, perceptions, and self-identity. *Context* can be social (e.g., culture, social connectedness) or material (e.g., infrastructure, geography). Contextual factors influence whether certain behaviours are possible and how certain cognitions can be acted upon. Context therefore shapes how the interplay between behaviours and cognitions constitutes lifestyle. This is important as lifestyle is not simply a matter of choice (1).

Three common perspectives on lifestyle emphasise patterns of behaviour, intentions and goals, or self-identity and social positioning. Behaviours, cognitions and contextual factors are the common elements of lifestyle in all three perspectives, but with different emphases.

A *patterned* perspective on lifestyles emphasises routine, habitual patterns of behaviour or consumption activity (2, 3). These behavioural patterns are context-specific and so are observable in the home, at work, on the move, during leisure time, and in other contexts (4, 5). Put simply, lifestyle describes “how people spend their money and their time” (6) or “how individuals live their lives” (1).

A *cognitive* perspective on lifestyles emphasises how intentions, problem awareness and other cognitions direct behaviours towards overarching goals (7). Lifestyles are therefore purposeful as well as responsive to context, and are linked to broader cognitive constructs such as values or worldviews (8).

A *reflexive* perspective on lifestyles emphasises how individuals organise and express their self-identity through their behaviour, while the behaviours then reflexively help constitute an individual’s identity (9). This reflexive perspective is associated with the work of the

sociologist, Anthony Giddens, who defined lifestyles as “routines that include the presentation of self, consumption, interaction and setting” (10). It blends the patterned perspective’s emphasis on routine behaviours with the cognitive perspective’s emphasis on both inward and outward-facing goals. The reflexive perspective also builds on a long historical tradition of research into lifestyles as a means of differentiating social position and status through outward signalling of identity. For example, Max Weber defined lifestyle as “a means of affirmation and differentiation of social status”.

Despite these differences in emphasis, the patterned, cognitive, and reflexive perspectives all recognise their dynamic and plural nature of lifestyles. This is reflected in the lack of convergence around a singular meaning or definition (see Box 1).

Box 1. Contrasting definitions of lifestyle.

Historical definitions of lifestyle

- “a means of affirmation and differentiation of social status” (Max Weber, 1864-1928)
- “a system of rules of conduct developed by individuals in order to attain their goals in life” (Alfred Adler, 1870-1937)
- “a consequence of culture, values, the symbolism of certain objects, moral values, and ethics” (11)
- “the system of constructs an individual elaborates and develops personally” (12)

Simple descriptive definitions of lifestyle

- “a way of living everyday life” (13)
- “how individuals live their lives” (1)
- “the way people live, and how they spend their money and time” (14)
- “the characteristic manner in which a person lives (or chooses to live) his or her life” (15)

Definitions emphasising patterned behaviours, routines and habits

- “habitual activity patterns woven into the practices of everyday life” (16)
- “a combination of modifiable behaviours that influence health” (17)
- “a way of living that influences and is reflected by one’s consumption behavior” (18)
- “consistency of behaviour and patterns of behaviour that are linked to values, socio-demographic characteristics and influenced by structural forces” (19)
- “a way of living selected by an individual which is expressed in both work and leisure behavior patterns ... and in activities, attitudes, interests, opinions, values and allocation of income” (20)
- “the behavioural patterns of individuals” (21)
- “a pattern of behavior conforming to the individual’s roles as household member, worker and leisure consumer subject to external constraints” (22)
- “the pattern of individual and social behavior characteristic of an individual or group ... which is usually expressed in behavior, but need not be” (23)
- “a set of habitual practices that can be understood as a result and a condition of everyday activities” (24, 25)
- “a pattern of attitudes and behaviours that are in some way consistent across an individual's life, or a particular domain of their life” (26)
- “expressed as typical attitudes and behaviour patterns” (27)
- “an approach to living that includes habitual behaviours and moral attitudes” (28)
- “a mixture of habits, conventional ways of doing things, and reasoned behavior” (29)
- “everyday actions and modes of consumption that form part of normal life” (30)
- “the way people live and influences on their behavior in consuming products or services” (31)

Definitions emphasising cognitions, intentions and goals

- “a mental construct, which is different from, but explains behaviour ... the system of cognitive categories, scripts, and their associations, which relate a set of products to a set of values” (32-35)

- "set of habits that are directed by the same main goal" (23)
- "the integration of an individual's system of values, attitudes, activities, and consumption methods" (36)
- "how people live and organize their priorities, integrating both big ideas and small practices" (37)
- "an intervening system of cognitive structures that link situation-specific product perceptions to increasingly abstract cognitive categories and finally to personal values" (38, 39)

Definitions emphasising self-identity, signalling, social positioning and differentiation

- "routines that include the presentation of self, consumption, interaction and setting" (10)
- "engagement in several related practices that construct and express a common aspect of self-identity" (40) also "a grouping of related practices that can reflect and inform the consumer's self-concept" (41)
- "the different personal actions that allow us to differentiate ourselves from others in society" (42)
- "a social construct that determines an individual's identification with a social group and manifests itself in all facets of everyday life, such as consumption habits and the demonstration of tastes" (24)
- "ways of doing, having, using and displaying our behavior and all the related products, objects and infrastructures" (43)
- "distinctive modes of existence that are accomplished by persons and groups through socially sanctioned and culturally intelligible patterns of action" (44)
- "consumption patterns shared by social groups or market segments" (45)

1.2 What is the difference between lifestyle and behaviour?

Lifestyles and behaviours are commonly used interchangeably in the literature. This is incorrect. Although lifestyles are observable through behaviours, lifestyles are not synonymous with behaviour. Behaviours are discrete actions associated with specific personal and contextual influences (depending on the analytical framework used). Lifestyles are made up of constellations of actions linked with some degree of consistency to broadly-defined cognitions and contexts (26).

Whereas behaviours are specific *within* a domain of everyday life (e.g., commuting behaviour, food purchasing behaviour), lifestyles are a meta-concept which tends to be applied *across* domains of everyday life. However, this is not always the case. The proposition for domain-specific lifestyles is based on an argument that a person's lifestyle need not be consistent across domains and therefore "descriptions of lifestyles should be restricted to specific life domains" (33, 34).

1.3 What is lifestyle change?

Definitions of lifestyle change tend to be specific to each research field with its characteristic interest in particular outcomes or impacts such as health or climate change. Research and practice seek to identify the potential for lifestyle change, the enabling and constraining factors for such lifestyle change, and the design of strategies and interventions to encourage or promote lifestyle change. Lifestyle change tends to be associated with public policy goals which help distinguish risky, undesirable, or 'worse' lifestyles from those which are desirable, consistent with broader social welfare, or 'better' from a societal perspective. However, lifestyle change can equally be applied by marketers or commercial firms seeking to position niche products and services or create brand associations linked to status or other private benefits.

Lifestyle change implies a before and an after state which can be linked causally: why do individuals change their lifestyles, and with what outcome? These two aspects of lifestyle change broadly distinguish intention and impact (46).

Lifestyle change may be motivated by intentions and a striving for self-consistency. For example, a green lifestyle is “a collection of practices by which people today try to address an interrelated set of environmental problems” (37). However, lifestyle change may also be caused by a change in contextual conditions. For example, lifestyles change when people migrate from the countryside into cities (47) or when new infrastructure is built (21), even people’s values and other cognitions remain the same.

There are also different impacts of lifestyle change on outcomes of interest. For example, change towards more healthy lifestyles may reduce risk factors associated with cardiovascular or respiratory disease (48). Change towards lower-carbon lifestyles can be identified by reductions in energy and material use or other consumption-based reductions in greenhouse gas emissions (43, 46).

It’s important to emphasise that the causes and outcomes of lifestyle change may not be consistent. For example, a climate scientist with strong environmental intentions may have a large carbon footprint as a result of frequent long-distance flights to participate in climate negotiations and conferences. Similarly, observed impacts of lifestyle change should not be used to infer intentions. For example, a household with a very low carbon footprint from minimal use of winter heating may have invested in energy-efficiency measures or may be living in fuel poverty. These tensions between behaviours, cognitions, and outcomes of interest from lifestyle change help reinforce that lifestyles are contextual and reflexively constructed, so can never offer a single unifying explanation for an individual's impact on emissions.

1.4 How are lifestyle and lifestyle change concepts applied?

Lifestyle and lifestyle change concepts are applied descriptively, analytically, and instrumentally.

Descriptively, lifestyle concepts are used to identify common groups of inter-related behaviours, and to characterise heterogeneity or clustering of similar individuals in a population. Marketing researchers can tease out a distinction between milieus (groups of like-minded people) and lifestyles (groups of similar behaviours) (49, 50). Linking lifestyle heterogeneity to contextual variation also helps identify which contextual factors most strongly shape lifestyles. For example, data from the periodic World Values Survey reveals systematic differences in lifestyles between regions with certain cultural characteristics such as pragmatism or respect for tradition. Variation can also be situational. For example, housing-related lifestyles are similar across different European countries whereas food-related lifestyles are not (33, 34).

Analytically, lifestyle concepts are used to explain or predict the consequences of lifestyles on outcomes of interest such as morbidity, expenditure, or greenhouse gas emissions. Specific lifestyle studies tend to define outcomes of interest quite narrowly. Examples from public health, marketing and environment research respectively are risk of dementia (51), food preferences (29), or propensity to buy an electric vehicle (9).

Instrumentally, lifestyle concepts are used to analyse how undesirable patterns of behaviours can be changed, and how differentiated interventions can be effectively targeted at specific lifestyle groups. Instrumental applications are therefore associated with lifestyle change. They can be strongly normative (i.e., based on prior assumptions about what is better) when tied to public policy objectives such as reducing ill health or ensuring clean air.

Any given study may combine all three applications of lifestyle concepts. For example, a national level study on the potential for low-carbon lifestyle change may first characterise lifestyle heterogeneity at the population level (descriptive), estimate carbon footprints for the different lifestyle groups (analytical), and then devise differentiated policy strategies for reducing carbon footprints in the high emitting groups as a basis for scenario modelling (instrumental) e.g., (43).

Lifestyle concepts are also applied in different fields of research and practice. The three main fields are: public health, marketing and consumer behaviour, and environment (including climate change). The remainder of this report synthesises literature from each of these three fields, and then concludes by drawing out insights for advancing research on low-carbon lifestyles.

2 A Public Health Perspective on Lifestyles and Lifestyle Change

Summary

The concept of lifestyle is widely applied in public health literature as a set of modifiable risk factors (e.g., inactivity, poor diet, obesity, smoking, alcohol excess and substance abuse). The constituent elements of lifestyle are patterns of behaviour (linked to health outcomes) that are outward expressions of cognitive processes. Health lifestyles are also shaped by contextual factors such as socio-economics and demography, and grounded in cultural identities and traditions. The concept of lifestyle in public health research is used in three main ways: *descriptively* to characterise lifestyle heterogeneity (e.g., health vulnerability); *analytically* to understand links between lifestyle elements and health outcomes; *instrumentally* to design lifestyle change interventions for managing or preventing chronic disease. Adjusting lifestyle practices to improve health and wellbeing involves a reassessment of values, attitudes and goals, within the constraints of personal circumstances. Integrative frameworks suggest that the challenges to public health and environmental sustainability are intertwined. Interventions to improve public health should be tailored to personal circumstances that empower the individual but are also directed at the wider social and physical environment which support and sustain healthy lifestyles.

2.1 How is lifestyle defined in public health? What are its constituent elements?

“Lifestyle is a way of living based on identifiable patterns of behaviour which are determined by the interplay between an individual’s personal characteristics, social interactions, and socioeconomic and environmental living conditions .. ”

“... There is no “optimal” lifestyle to be prescribed for all people. Culture, income, family structure, age, physical ability, home and work environment will make certain ways and conditions of living more attractive, feasible and appropriate” World Health Organisation (52p.16).

Lifestyle is a commonly used concept in public health, but despite this quite comprehensive entry in the Health Promotion Glossary, it is rarely and explicitly defined in public health literature. Lifestyle is presented as a set of multiple modifiable risk factors (48, 53). A lifestyle that builds health resilience (54) is associated with better disease outcomes (55). Conversely, an unhealthy lifestyle is associated with increased risk of chronic disease (56). Lifestyles are represented by particular behaviours (57) that include diet and nutrition, physical activity, alcohol consumption, smoking status, wellbeing and emotional resilience (58). Graham and White (16) describe these behaviours or habitual activity patterns as *“woven into the practices of everyday life”*. Healthy lifestyles generally promote regular physical exercise, calorie-controlled nutrient rich diets, avoidance of smoking and alcohol excess (17, 51, 55). Underlying this behaviour-defined lifestyle, is a more implicit acknowledgement of the importance of attitudes, perceptions and interpersonal relations e.g., (54).

Risk-focused conceptualisations of lifestyle in public health e.g., (17, 48)) tend to be developed around modifiable behaviours associated with specific situations and habitual practices such as a sedentary lifestyle, poor diet and substance abuse. Other conceptual

frameworks such as the Health Promoting Lifestyle Profile (HPLP) (59) and the ‘total health framework’ (58) also include cognitive dimensions that are related to emotional resilience, health responsibility, and interpersonal relations (54). Values and beliefs shape lifestyles and health consequences (1). This interplay between cognitive processes and ‘traditional’ lifestyle risk factors is embedded in a contextual layer that includes broad societal level factors such as social deprivation e.g., (53) and polygenic variation (51).

In sum, from a public health perspective, the constituent elements of lifestyle are patterns of behaviour (associated with particular health outcomes) that are the outward observable actions of cognitive processes (60, 61). Lifestyles are also shaped by contextual factors such as socio-economic settings (including education, income, and social norms), demographic factors (such as gender and life stage), and grounded in cultural identities and traditions. Table 1 summarises the constituent elements of lifestyles and lifestyle change from the perspective of public health. (See Appendices for further details of the underlying studies).

Table 1. Lifestyle elements used in public health studies.

Lifestyle type	Behaviours, practices, modifiable risk factors	Cognitions	Contexts
Healthy lifestyle	Non-smoker, healthy diet (e.g., calorie-controlled, low in salt, red meat and processed foods, rich in fruit and vegetables), regular physical activity, sufficient sleep, regulated alcohol consumption.	Knowledge of risk factors and disease, positive attitude, perceived responsibility, purpose in life, feeling at peace with oneself, emotional resilience, mindfulness, stress management, strong social relationships.	Socio-economic conditions (e.g., higher income / level of education), socio-cultural heritage supportive of healthy living (e.g., Mediterranean diet and culture, cycling in the Netherlands), good access to health care, low exposure to toxins.
Unhealthy lifestyle	Smoker, unhealthy diet resulting in poor weight management, physically inactive / sedentary lifestyle, insufficient sleep, excessive alcohol consumption, substance abuse.	Low awareness of disease risk factors, negative attitude to health, psychosocial stress, depression, lack of motivation or goal setting, weak social networks, weak sense of community.	Socio-economic conditions (e.g., social deprivation, ready access to cheap unhealthy food, limited access to exercise facilities / health services, sedentary job), social norms associated with poor diet or physical inactivity, high exposure to toxins.
Promoting and sustaining healthy lifestyles	Lifestyle behaviours (e.g., diet and exercise) that are tailored to particular health outcomes such as reducing the risk of hypertension, type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and dementia.	Clear and specific goals, knowledge of the association between lifestyle factors and disease, motivation, self-efficacy, stress management, wellbeing, social connectedness.	Availability of resources to support healthy lifestyle choices, community group support, access to counselling services, environment supportive of physical exercise

2.2 What are the main applications of lifestyle concepts in public health?

In public health research, the concept of lifestyle is used in three main ways: *descriptively* to characterising lifestyle groups and heterogeneity; *analytically* to understand links between lifestyle elements and outcomes of interest; *instrumentally* to design lifestyle change interventions.

First, lifestyle segmentation or categorisation is used to target groups of individuals that are particularly vulnerable or for which intervention strategies may be most effective. Studies tend to adopt a patterned behavioural approach in which lifestyle groups are identified using the weighted or unweighted total score across a set of lifestyle factors. Contextual influences (such as social deprivation) are found to be associated with groups defined by less healthy lifestyle behaviours. For example, the Office for National Statistics (1) found the lowest healthy life expectancy cluster was associated with lower scores of healthy lifestyle factors and have more long-term sickness or disability in the UK.

Second, lifestyle is used as a marker of some specific aspect of health. For example, a systematic review and meta-analysis found that the relative risks of mortality decreased proportionate to a higher number of healthy lifestyle factors (17). This study conceptualised lifestyle as patterned behaviours. However, Aliberti, Cavallo (54) adopted a more cognitive approach in their study of lifestyle as an indicator of wellbeing and academic performance.

Third, lifestyle is used as a tool for either preventing or managing chronic disease. Examples include physician counselling on lifestyle behaviour modification to facilitate patient management of hypertension (55), and group-based lifestyle intervention to promote and sustain weight loss (60). Lifestyle measurement instruments such as the HPLP have been used to assess the effectiveness of interventions. Bodai, Nakata (58) reviewed lifestyle medicine and found growing evidence that healthy lifestyle choices can avert chronic conditions such as cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes, and made a passionate call on the medical community to effectively implement and share the power of lifestyle medicine. Faiola, Papautsky (61) argued that chronic diseases can be managed effectively with the use of technology such as apps that empower patients to adopt and sustain healthy lifestyles through self-regulation. Viewing lifestyle as a tool for improving health outcomes exemplifies a reflexive approach in which motivational skills training, personalised goal setting, and developing inner resilience are the precursor to behaviour modification.

Each of these three applications is discussed in more detail in the sections that follow.

2.3 How is lifestyle measured in public health? What data are used?

Structured questionnaires are commonly used to measure lifestyle elements including: attitudes to eating or to self, quality of life (54); lifestyle practices such as smoking, alcohol consumption, diet & nutrition, and physical activity (1, 17, 48, 51, 53). Contextual variables measured include socioeconomic or demographic variables (53, 54). Table 2 provides examples.

Lifestyle factors relevant to particular health outcomes have also been identified through structured review (62, 63), narrative review (13) and through systematic review and meta-analysis (17).

Studies with a focus on initiating or sustaining lifestyle change tend to use a mixed methods approach that considers risk factors for disease (e.g., physical activity and diet), cognitive variables (such as knowledge, beliefs, and self-efficacy), medical characteristics (such as blood pressure and cholesterol levels), and socio-demographic variables (such as age, education and income) (55, 60).

Data of relevance to public health includes clinical metrics, socio-demographic, behavioural, psychological, and environmental information. The multiplicity of relevant data collected cover a wide variety of sources and measurement tools (see Appendices for further details). Primary data are collected through structured and semi-structured questionnaires, food diaries, and clinical observations and tests. Established questionnaires (validated and tested for reliability) such as the HPLP II questionnaire are applied to new areas of research or in different cultural settings (64). The UK Biobank is a large prospective health resource documenting the health and wellbeing of around 500,000 participants (www.ukbiobank.ac.uk). This resource has been mined to identify lifestyles associated with cardiovascular disease mortality and all-cause mortality (53) and with the incidence of dementia (51). The Office for National Statistics compiles information that enables a contextualising of health outcomes in the UK, according to differences in lifestyles (1).

2.4 How are different lifestyle groups identified in public health?

Public health research has different ways of distinguishing lifestyle groups (Table 2). Some studies on modifiable risk factors representing lifestyle elements are used as independent variables to estimate a particular health outcome e.g., (17, 54). Lifestyle groups represent levels of healthiness (51, 53) or they represent heterogeneous combinations of risk factors.

Common methods for identifying lifestyle groups include latent class analysis of unhealthy behaviours to produce risk classes which can then be associated with socioeconomic and demographic variables (48), factor analysis of lifestyle elements (64), and cluster analysis based on attitudes and behaviours (65). For example, Atzendorf, Apfelbacher (48) use latent class analysis to identify four heterogeneous lifestyle groups in Germany, a ‘healthy lifestyle’, ‘risky drinking lifestyle’, ‘smoking lifestyle’ and a ‘cumulate risk factors lifestyle’.

Lifestyles are thus classified according to the relationships between defined elements (53), and may be weighted to adjust sample data for variation in gender, age or genetic traits (51). Identification of lifestyle groups is viewed as a useful tool for targeting or prioritising health promotion strategies and health behaviour intervention (48).

The frameworks and methods summarised in Table 2 for identifying lifestyle groups in public health are commonly implemented either as part of case studies of specific risk groups (which control for variation in context) or as part of population-level studies with nationally-representative samples (which have to account for variation in contextual influences). Although both approaches share similar analytical frameworks and methods, case study approaches are closely linked to targeted intervention strategies, while national studies provide clearer evidence that wider aspects of the physical and social environment have an influence on lifestyle behaviours related to health. In the UK, for example, Foster, Celis-Morales (53) found that unhealthy lifestyles were associated with disproportionate harm in areas of socio-economic deprivation.

Table 2. Analytical frameworks for distinguishing lifestyle groups in public health.

Lifestyle study focus	Study	Variables measured	Measurement tools	Lifestyle group identification
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Lifestyle factors associated with a specific health outcome.	Aliberti, Cavallo (54)	Sociodemographic, personal health, attitudes, quality of life.	HPLP II questionnaire (scale responses).	HPLP items used as independent variables
	Kuan, Kueh (64)	52 items developed around six domains	HPLP II questionnaire (scale responses)	Factor analysis.
	Atzendorf, Apfelbacher (48)	Eight lifestyle practices representing risk factors.	Pre-existing survey on substance abuse	Latent Class Analysis
	Foster, Celis-Morales (53)	Socioeconomic variables, unhealthy lifestyle practices.	UK Biobank; prospective population-based cohort	Categorised according to unweighted lifestyle score.
	Lourida, Hannon (51)	4 lifestyle practices (smoking, physical activity, diet, alcohol consumption)	UK Biobank; retrospective cohort study	Categories based on lifestyle factor scores weighted by socio-demographic variables
	Office for National Statistics (1)	5 lifestyle practices (smoking, BMI, physical activity, diet, alcohol consumption)	Existing health data by upper tier local authority (UTLAs)	Lifestyle factors for the 7 highest UTLAs ranked by Health Life Expectancy
	Loef and Walach (17)	5 lifestyle practices (smoking, BMI, physical activity, diet, alcohol consumption)	Systematic review and meta-analysis of 15 longitudinal / prospective studies	Combinations of lifestyle factors considered as independent variables
Lifestyle intervention and health promotion strategies	Andjelkovic (55)	Sociodemographic variables, medical characteristics, physical exercise, smoking, diet, self-management strategies, knowledge & beliefs	Structured questionnaire to assess adherence to healthy lifestyle	None
	Faiola, Papautsky (61)	Scenario narrative (retired, overweight, inactive, pre-type II diabetes)	Theoretical development: mHealthy Lifestyle Management Model	None
	Jamal, Moy (60)	Clinical measures, diet, alcohol, smoking, physical activity, cognitive processes, socio-demographic variables.	Questionnaires: physical activity, psychological measures, QoL, automatic thought	Unhealthy lifestyle. Baseline and end of programme measures assessed intervention.
	Minich and Bland (63)	Recommendations for diet, activity, environment, stress	Literature review: Personalised lifestyle medicine	Interaction between lifestyle factors, and biomarkers, symptoms, genetics, epigenetics.
Integrated lifestyle models	Dernini, Berry (13)	Nutrition & diet, physical activity, environment, economy, society & culture.	Narrative review to develop: Mediterranean diet as a healthy & sustainable lifestyle	None
	Pícha and Navrátil (65)	15 items for 5 factors: sustainable economy, healthy lifestyle, personal development, alternative health care, ecological lifestyles	Lifestyle of Health and Sustainability (LOHAS), scaled responses	Confirmatory factor analysis, cluster analysis for market segmentation
	Quam, Rocklöv (62)	Active transport (cycling / walking), diet (reduced	Structured review to identify lifestyle	None

		consumption of animal products)	choices with environment-health co-benefits.	
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2.5 What is the link between healthy lifestyles and sustainable lifestyles?

Common analytical frameworks such as the Health Promoting Lifestyle Profile (HPLP) are developed around lifestyle constructs covering individual practices associated with health, attitudes, mental resilience and social relationships (54, 64). Some studies have broadened the conceptualisation of healthy lifestyles to encompass sustainable lifestyles. For example, Graham and White (16) developed an integrated framework that draws on shared evidences and common features from the different fields of public health and environmental sustainability. This builds on the UN Millennium Ecosystem Assessment Health Synthesis Report (66). Lifestyle is viewed as a ‘bridging’ concept between public health and environmental sustainability, and a key driver of change (16).

The Lifestyle of Health and Sustainability (LOHAS) framework draws on perspectives from marketing, public health and sustainability to characterise lifestyle around five main categories: sustainable economy, healthy lifestyles, personal development, alternative health care, and ecological lifestyles (65, 67).

The ‘Med Diet 4.0’ framework is developed around four themes, nutrition & health, environment, society & culture, and the economy (13). The more plant-based diet of the Mediterranean has perceived health and environment benefits, with high socio-cultural value encouraging principles of mutual awareness, resource frugality, and the promotion of traditional crafts and skills.

These integrative frameworks are premised on the challenges to public health and environmental sustainability being intertwined. Lifestyle choices such as active transport and consuming a more plant-based diet have the potential both to protect the environment and to improve health (62).

2.6 What is lifestyle change in public health?

There is good evidence that chronic conditions are influenced by lifestyle, and lifestyle change can avert poor health outcomes (58, 63). Lifestyle change from a public health perspective involves adopting and maintaining a lifestyle that is beneficial to the health and wellbeing of both individuals and society. Strategies that promote healthy lifestyles can be identified on the basis of risk factors for vulnerable population groups (48). Gray, Kross (56) highlight the need for a theoretical basis to lifestyle change, to understand the drivers and the tendency for lifestyle practices to cluster (those with a healthy diet tend not to smoke and are more physically active). The ability and motivation to implement and sustain lifestyle change is associated with individual differences in psychological processes, such as a sense of individual responsibility (56), knowledge, individual empowerment (61), beliefs, self-management (55), self-efficacy and social support (60). Physical and social environments can further sustain or undermine lifestyle change (56, 57, 61).

2.7 How is lifestyle change promoted in public health?

“Individual lifestyles, characterized by identifiable patterns of behaviour, can have a profound effect on an individual’s health and on the health of others. If health is to be improved by enabling individuals to change their lifestyles, action must be directed not only at the individual but also at the social and living conditions which interact to produce and maintain these patterns of behaviour.” (66)

Understanding the reasons for, and context to, lifestyle activities is a prerequisite for developing public health intervention strategies. From the broadest perspective, adjusting lifestyle practices to improve health and wellbeing involves a reassessment of values, attitudes and goals, within the constraints of personal circumstances.

A number of intervention strategies have been reviewed in the public health literature (see Appendices for details). Motivation is key to the initiation of lifestyle change (17). Middleton, Anton (57) outline four constructs of lifestyle change: knowledge, self-efficacy beliefs, self-regulatory skills and barriers to overcome. The first two constructs are important aspects of the initiation process; knowledge and appreciation of the risks of lifestyle behaviours on health outcomes, and self-efficacy and constructive beliefs. In a health care setting, initiation can take the form of counselling in which relevant information is provided at appropriate ‘teaching moments’ (56) and short-term achievable goals identified (57).

There are a range of intervention approaches to improve health through lifestyle change. These comprise one-off or regular counselling sessions (55), group intervention programs, and the practice of lifestyle medicine (58). Group intervention programs capitalise on the strength of connectedness, offering moral support, group discussion and feedback. Personalised lifestyle medicine (56, 63), arises from the concept that one size does not fill all in regard to a healthy lifestyle. Instead, recommendations are tailored for individual clinical characteristics, biomarkers and genetic variants. Alongside these general approaches to intervention, there are a range of specific tools or strategies. Faiola, Papautsky (61) frame these strategies around an ‘inform – coach – empower’ pathway. Patients and practitioners require relevant information on the benefits of lifestyle change for improving health and avoiding or managing chronic disease. Coaching is undertaken vis-à-vis group or one-to-one counselling, and involves cognitive behaviour therapy, stress management, and specific skills training (e.g., for handling situational cues and setbacks). The patient is empowered through self-management skills and developing inner resilience. Technology apps can be harnessed to share information, provide patient-generated data and allow self-monitoring (61) which develops self-regulatory skills (57).

Barriers (cognitive and contextual) impede the process of lifestyle change adoption and adherence (56, 57, 60, 61). The cognitive barriers are associated with a lack of appreciation about risks and health benefits of lifestyle behaviours, complacency, and feelings of low self-esteem, disbelief or negativity following minor lapses. Contextual barriers related to the physical and social environment are wide-ranging. In the community, unhealthy lifestyles may be the social norm. Intentions to reduce weight and improve nutrition are hindered by an overabundance of inexpensive unhealthy food and overexposure to advertising of such goods (57). Targets to increase physical activity are hampered by a lack of access to exercise facilities and the pervasiveness of sedentary jobs. There may be insufficient time or

resources invested in implementing intervention programs or providing counselling sessions (58). In addition, cultural and ethnic influences can further undermine or restrict lifestyle choices (1).

Poor adherence to lifestyle change is widespread particularly in the longer term. Middleton, Anton (57) outlined the factors reducing adherence to lifestyle change. These include environment (access to unhealthy food, lack of exercise facilities), sociocultural conditions (sedentary jobs, limited leisure time) and psychological influences (e.g., perceived stress). However, there are a number of strategies (cognitive and contextual) that are found to be more effective for sustaining healthy lifestyle change. Foremost are those related to cognitive processes, enhancing self-regulatory skills, and building inner resilience (64) through overcoming obstacles and setbacks. Widening the support network (through friends and family, buddy systems and group-based programs) also improves the chance of long-term adherence (57). Regulations and policies should be directed at promoting healthy lifestyle change programs as beneficial for individuals and the wider society (1, 17). Specifically, these should encourage infrastructure supportive of maintaining a healthy lifestyle (e.g., access to exercise facilities, well-connected networks of pathways and cycle routes, and regulated advertising of unhealthy products). In addition, policies should address social inequalities and deprivation that have been linked to unhealthy lifestyles and poor health outcomes (53). Faiola, Papautsky (61) advanced an integrated 'mHealthy Lifestyle Management' model that involves five steps (Inform - Engage - Empower - Partner - Support) embedded in and interacting with a dynamic physical and social environment (the 'mHealthy' stands for mobile health).

There are lessons to be learnt from health approaches to lifestyle change. Lifestyle modification requires a comprehensive approach in which recommendations are individualised for clinical characteristics (63) and personal circumstances and contexts (62). Lifestyle medicine is a term used to describe the prescription of a set of lifestyle behaviours to improve health outcomes. Minich and Bland (63) review the complex interaction between lifestyle factors (nutrition, physical activity, stress management and environmental exposure) with individual biomarkers, genetic variants and epigenetic modification. This illustrates the potential benefits of personalised lifestyle medicine that is tailored to individual biomarkers, genetics and epigenetic variations, and individual circumstances.

Targeted changes in lifestyle behaviours should be accompanied by strategies that enhance cognitive processes and engage the support of the wider community (60). There is also growing evidence that multi-component intervention programs (e.g., combining counselling sessions with group-based sessions) are more effective than single-strategy approaches (57, 60).

3 A Marketing and Consumer Behaviour Perspective on Lifestyles and Lifestyle Change

Summary

From the perspective of marketing and consumer behaviour, lifestyle is simply viewed as a way of everyday life that leads to choices between goods, services and expenditure. More complex framings recognise these choices reflect values, intentions and opinions as consumers are complex decision makers. Marketing practitioners use lifestyle classifications to segment markets and position products and services relative to specific lifestyle groups. Lifestyle change is explained by shifts in the lifestyle landscape. This includes changes in contextual and cognitive factors that influence consumption patterns. Lifestyle change can be encouraged using marketing techniques which can also be applied as social marketing to encourage choices with public good benefits.

3.1 What does lifestyle mean in marketing? What constitutes a consumer lifestyle?

Marketing is a fairly new science. It emerged as part of a growing consumer culture in the USA during the 1950s (68, 69). Lifestyle marketing is a process of establishing relationships between products offered in the market and targeted lifestyle groups (70).

In marketing, lifestyle is simply defined as a 'way of everyday life' that leads to 'choices between goods and services' and 'expenditure' (31, 36, 71-73). These patterns are distinguished by social character observable in individual socio-demographic characteristics (36, 74).

Cognitive and reflexive lifestyle perspectives in marketing frame consumers as complex decision makers whose choices reflect their values, intentions and opinions (36). These choices are shaped by structural forces including social structures, ideology and socio-cultural differentiation (19, 50), self-expression and personal ideology (49, 72).

3.2 What is lifestyle used for in marketing?

"People are diverse, but their values, dreams, and attitudes place them in distinct lifestyle groups" (75).

Marketing is fundamentally a science of persuasion (69). Marketing practitioners use lifestyle concepts descriptively to research and identify lifestyle segments, and analytically and reflexively to position products and services in a way that appeals to like-minded consumers (20, 68). An early proprietary lifestyle classification system was developed in the 1970s by social scientist Mitchell (75). The values and lifestyle classification (VALS) drew on early motivation theory (Maslow's hierarchy of needs 1954), and the concept of social character (76) to identify nine distinctive lifestyles. It had a 'dramatic' impact on marketing approaches in the USA during the late 1970s (74). There are now many proprietary lifestyle classifications including the Sinus-Milieus, Euro-Socio Style, Roper Consumer Styles, and Mosaic lifestyle classifications (see below for further details) (20).

3.3 What approaches and frameworks are used in marketing to measure lifestyles?

Measuring lifestyles from a marketing perspective consists of two key approaches: the AIO framework, and the value systems approach. The AIO (attitudes, interests and opinions) framework was introduced by Lazer (11). Lifestyle is defined as the manner in which people conduct their lives and includes their activities, interests and opinions (29). Activities consist of manifest actions and include work, leisure, community, shopping. Interests relate to objects, events or topics and include family, home, work, and achievement. Opinions include a range of beliefs relating to one's self, products, society, culture, the future (31, 71). Typical statements could include "I drive my car daily" (activity), "I am not very interested in electric cars" (interest), "climate change is not important" (opinion). The broad framing means it is generalizable across domains or countries. Srihadi, Hartoyo (31) use AIO to identify four distinctive tourism-related lifestyle clusters. Hur, Kim (14) use AIO to identify six distinctive food related lifestyle clusters. Jain (71) use AIO to identify three distinctive consumption clusters in India. In all these studies lifestyle is measured using a multi-item survey from which unique lifestyle groups are identified using cluster analysis.

In the value systems approach, values are defined as guiding principles in people's lives that vary in importance (77). Unlike the AIO approach, the value systems approach uses a set of predetermined value statements adapted from the Rokeach Value Survey (78). This lists 18 different statements, distinguishing between two key dimensions. These are the inner and the outer self. Value items include the importance of 'self-respect', 'happiness', 'freedom', 'friendship', 'social recognition', 'national security', 'a world at peace'. The VALS lifestyle classification model (75) and the List of Values (LOV) (74) are aligned with this approach. Another important scale for assessing value systems was developed by Schwartz (79) and includes 56 values. Ten of these are measured within the World Values Survey which explores values and beliefs across almost 100 countries.

Hybrid approaches across these frameworks are not uncommon. For example Vyncke (77) developed the values, life visions, and aesthetic lifestyle typology (V-L-A). This takes a value systems approach adding further constructs related to life vision, aesthetic styles, media preferences, product attributes (cars, tourism, political parties), and demographics. For cars attributes included safety, design, engine power and reliability.

There are a range of other frameworks that align variously with these two approaches. For example, the food-related lifestyle model sees lifestyle as a mixture of habits, conventional ways of doing things, and reasoned behaviour (29). It is based on the simple attitude, behaviour, context (ABC) model (80) which is a specific representation of the three lifestyle elements: behaviours, cognitions, and context. Using this framework, Nie and Zepeda (29) distinguish four food-related lifestyle clusters, and Sanquist, Orr (44) distinguish between three energy-related lifestyle clusters (see Appendices for further details of relevant studies).

The voluntary simplicity lifestyle scale was developed by Leonard-Barton (81). It relates to an anti-materialistic lifestyle ideology defined as "*lifestyle choice that involves minimalizing consumption and divorcing oneself from material possessions*". It is associated with green, ethical, and sustainable consumption (19). A number of empirical studies have tested and identified variants of this scale. Cengiz and Torlak (19) use an online survey to test 15 items related to recycling behaviour, food (eating, growing), preference for physical forms of

transport (walking, cycling), self-reliance (making things) and use of the second hand economy. They distinguish a single lifestyle group (voluntary simplicity). Rich, Wright (82) use a variety of qualitative and quantitative methods to test 67 items related to growing food, environmental attitudes, pragmatism, and spending.

3.4 What lifestyle groups are identified in marketing research?

Empirical studies identifying lifestyle clusters in marketing tend to use proprietary frameworks (Table 3), and focus on particular behavioural ‘contexts’ such as food, leisure and tourism, and energy use, as well as generalised consumption. Studies using national samples (USA, Europe, Asia, New Zealand) independently identified distinct lifestyle clusters. One of these draws on a nationally representative database of energy use (44). These empirical studies are valuable because they are fully transparent and offer key insights into measurement frameworks, analytical approaches, and detailed findings.

There are also a number of market research organisations that have a wider geographical reach and representation. These offer proprietary segmentation tools (at a cost) to help organisations (and governments) identify generalisable cross-national lifestyle clusters. As they use different definitions and models, they tend to arrive at different lifestyle groups (Table 3).

An important contribution of these proprietary frameworks is their focus on socio-cultural dimensions of lifestyle which include constructs such as inequality and ‘milieu’. The concept of milieu was developed in the 1990s by the Vester group and the Sinus Institute. ‘Milieu’ is defined as “sub-cultural units within a society which group together people with a similar view of life and way of life” (50).

Table 3. Proprietary frameworks for identifying national and cross-national lifestyle groups

	Lifestyle items	Main factors or dimensions	Lifestyle groups (prevalence)	Location and sample size
Sinus-Milieu	items related to social status (socio-demographics) value orientation (aim in life, ideals, society) way of living (interests, leisure activities, social life, occupation attitudes towards work, family, leisure, work ethos, performance, aesthetic needs) consumption (leisure activities, social life)	two dimensions 1. social status (income, education, occupation) 2. degree of modernisation (from traditional to liberal). a distinguishing character is that lifestyle groups are not discrete but are allowed to overlap	<u>10 lifestyle groups</u> 1. modern mainstreamers (12.6%) 2. adaptive navigators (11.1%) 3. traditionalists (11.1%) 4. precarious (9.2%) 5. hedonists (14.8%) 6. established (10.0%) 7. liberal intellectuals (7.4%) 8. performers (7.9%) 9. cosmopolitan avant-gardes (8.7%) 10. social ecologists (7.3%)	latest database update: 3,000 qualitative and 300,000 quantitative interviews. (transnational model, German origin)
Euro-Socio-Styles	items include income, marital status (single, married, children), age, view of others, social engagement, aspirations, education	two dimensions contrasting differing needs 1. stability versus transformation 2. illusion versus reality	<u>8 different Euro styles</u> 1. new world 2. cosy tech world 3. crafty world 4. magic world 5. authentic world 6. secure world 7. steady world 8. standing world	survey (n=24,000) from 15 countries in Europe

Rope-Consumer-Styles	items include: openness to new things, traditional values, thriftiness, conservativeness, age, status/wealth, concerned with appearance / reputation, responsibility, favourite brands, family structure, faith, habits, personal interests, ambitions, personality traits, attitude to the environment	two dimensions contrasting differing needs 1. passionate life versus peace and security 2. materialism and price orientation versus post materialism and quality orientation (need to have versus need to be)	<u>8 lifestyle groups</u> 1. dreamers 2. adventurers 3. open-minded 4. homebodies 5. rational-realists 6. organics 7. settled 8. demanding	survey (n=35,000) from 25 core countries and changing additional countries
MOSAIC	demographic, geographic and psychographic items include: income, influence, country of origin, consumer behaviour, residential location, values, interests, marital status, and travel mode.	multidimensional: young-elderly, asset poor-asset rich, high density-low density, low income-high income, traditional-cosmopolitan	<u>15 groups and 66 detailed types (Experian, 2015a):</u> A. city prosperity (3.5%) B. prestige positions (8.2%) C. country living (4.4%) D. rural reality (8.7%) E. senior security (4.3%) F. suburban stability (11.2%) G. domestic success (5.8%) H. aspiring homemakers (5.9%) I. family basics (8.7%) J. transient renters (5.2%) K. municipal challenge (5.2%) L. vintage value (5.9%) M. modest traditions (7.4%) N. urban cohesion (7.0%) O. rental hubs (8.5%)	49 million individuals and 26 million households. Method available in more than 29 countries but focus is on UK.
Research Institute on Social Change (RISC)	items cover: demographic; attitudes regarding fashions, institutions, environment; ambitions; consumption; ethical values; global outlook	3 dimensions: 1. exploration/stability 2. social/individual 3. global/local	1. researchers & explorers, 2. mobile networkers, 3. searchers of security, 4. enrooted traditionalists 5. worriers 6. energetic searchers for amusement and pleasure 7. guardians, 8. ethical signposts 9. social climbers, 10. greedy consumers	based on measurements in more than 40 countries, mostly European. Longitudinal surveys are conducted.
VALS2	18 value statements related based on Rokeach (78)Rokeach [1973] plus additional items that reflect values and interests in technology and social character (e.g., status)	two main dimensions: 1. self-orientation 2. resources	1. actualisers/innovators (8%) 2. thinkers (11%) 3. achievers (13%) 4. experiencers (12%) 5. believers (16%) 6. strivers (13%) 7. makers (15%) 8. survivors (14%)	proprietary framework developed in USA, with transnational application but cultural variants in proliferation of clusters

3.5 What is lifestyle change in marketing?

Lifestyle research in marketing seeks to constantly evaluate what is referred to as ‘the lifestyle landscape’ (20). Lifestyle change in marketing is observed by shifts in consumption patterns, related to changes in contextual and cognitive factors. Contextual factors include greater structural flexibility in terms of people’s working and private lives, erosion of family

structure, digitalisation of day-to-day living, and growing polarisation of wealth (49). Cognitive factors include shifts in attitudes and values, beliefs or ideology which challenge the dominant consumer culture (19, 72). For example, the term 'voluntary simplicity' defines a group of consumers who adapt their daily lifestyles towards an anti-materialistic lifestyle philosophy (19, 45, 82).

In marketing, lifestyle characterises individuals but is also socially motivated. Starr (83) argues that people adopt lifestyles common to their social groups and then modify them in standard ways as they age or follow lifecycle norms. Social marketing is described by Kotler and Zaltman (84) as an approach to planned social change. It involves the use of marketing techniques applied to a social idea or public benefit (such as healthy or sustainable lifestyles). Interventions can occur at the individual level, but are more likely to be successful where the motivation for change comes from the community or where promising social groups act as role models or opinion leaders (7). Seegebarth, Peyer (45) suggests that this approach can redirect consumption from ecologically-friendly products to the question of whether consumption itself is necessary.

4 A Pro-Environmental and Low-Carbon Perspective on Lifestyles and Lifestyle Change

Summary

Like public health and marketing, pro-environmental and low-carbon research identifies behaviours, cognitions and context as the three common and interacting elements of lifestyle. As many different domains of everyday life are associated with environmental impacts, lifestyle concepts can be applied narrowly in specific domains like food, homes, and travel, as well as in a general integrative way across domains. There are also many inconsistencies in the behaviours, cognitions and contexts which make up low-carbon lifestyles: between knowledge and action; between values and action; and between action in different domains. This means it is problematic to identify low-carbon lifestyles from behavioural patterns alone.

Lifestyle concepts are applied in low-carbon research descriptively to characterise low and high impact behaviours in similar lifestyle groups, and analytically to assess options for reducing energy use or carbon emissions. Such applications tend to take a patterned view of lifestyle with its emphasis on routine or high frequency behaviours. Lifestyle concepts are also applied instrumentally to design or evaluate interventions for encouraging low-carbon lifestyle change. These instrumental applications tend to take a cognitive view of lifestyle with its emphasis on values, intentions, and individual responsibility. There are also some examples of reflexive approaches to low-carbon lifestyles in which individuals adopt pro-environmental behaviours to differentiate themselves from others in society.

A variety of quantitative and qualitative methods are used to measure lifestyle elements, ranging from large sample quantitative surveys for characterising lifestyle heterogeneity, to focus groups and interviews for developing narrative themes of sustainable living. These identify low-carbon lifestyles in five different ways, based on: (i) extent of pro-environmental behaviours and commitment; (ii) basic orientations towards technology, society, and the environment; (iii) inward- and outward-looking perceptions of the self and the world; (iv) consistency between behaviours and cognitions across different contexts; (v) contextual determinants of lifestyle such as affluence or location.

Low-carbon lifestyle change is most commonly framed from a cognitive perspective as being motivated and intentional, either with respect to specific behaviours, or more broadly to construct a consistent self-identity or standing within the world. Interventions tested range from short-term targeted campaigns to educate and inform (which blur the distinction between behaviour change and lifestyle change) and longer-term systemic shifts in infrastructure, regulatory measures and social structures (which blur the distinction between system change and lifestyle change).

4.1 What are low-carbon lifestyles?

Research on pro-environmental, sustainable, green or low-carbon lifestyles is variously concerned with what the adverse impacts of lifestyles are on environmental conditions, and on how and why people may seek to reduce these adverse impacts. In this section, we use 'low-carbon lifestyles' as shorthand for these different emphases.

Low-carbon lifestyles are defined and conceptualised in wide-ranging ways, reflecting patterns of behaviours, intentional action, and the shaping influences of the wider social and physical environment (Box 2). Contextual factors such as institutions and infrastructures can lock-in unsustainable behaviours and habits (85).

An important but often tacit distinction in low-carbon lifestyles research is between domain-specific lifestyles and 'general' lifestyles across domains. Do we have a single lifestyle? Or a lifestyle specific to food, leisure, travel, homes, or energy use? Low-carbon lifestyles research assumes both. This differs from public health and marketing as it fragments integrative lifestyle concepts into specific behavioural domains or contexts. One consequence is that the 'lifestyle' in low-carbon research becomes closer in meaning to 'behaviour'.

General lifestyles across domains

Cognitive or reflexive perspectives on low-carbon lifestyles broadly consider "how we live our everyday lives" and "how we socialise, exchange, share, educate and build identities" (UNEP 2010). General lifestyles thus comprise both behaviours and cognitions (e.g., values, beliefs, environmental awareness, attitudes, intentions) which reflect household patterns of living. Cognitions as an "organising and guiding construct in a person's life" are particularly important in low-carbon lifestyles (33).

A majority of the low-carbon studies reviewed considered lifestyles across multiple domains such as food, energy, manufactured products, transport, tourism and leisure (28, 85-88). This approach helps identify salient lifestyle elements associated with environmental impacts. Sustainability lifestyle frameworks provide a way of organising, thinking, planning, and evaluating strategies for reducing adverse impacts (89, 90). Such studies inform social marketing and educational campaigns to encourage more sustainable lifestyles (2, 90).

The general multi-domain conceptualisation of lifestyle also lends itself to analytical assessments. These include lifestyle-based modelling analysis of how consumption and daily activity impacts carbon emissions or other environmental impacts or ecological footprints (18, 28, 47). General lifestyle frameworks are also used to assess the relationships between sustainable practices and wellbeing (91) or beliefs and attitudes (92) as well as perceptions and acceptability of environmental policy instruments (87).

Domain-specific lifestyles

As well as general frameworks of low-carbon lifestyles across domains, many studies focus narrowly on lifestyles in specific domains of resource-intensive activity. The many different examples include domestic energy use and waste generation (92), dwelling location and type (22, 33), mobility and travel (24, 35), leisure and tourism (5), and food (14, 34). Low-carbon lifestyles are also tested as generalisable explanations for technology adoption decisions in different domains, such as electric vehicles, solar panels and green electricity tariffs (9). Some studies find that much of the variation in energy or resource consumption can be explained by domain-specific lifestyle factors (44).

Comparative studies of context-specific lifestyles assess variation in behaviours and cognitions across different physical environments: e.g., rural or urban residents, transitional sites from home through journey to holiday destination, social settings such as members

and non-members of grass roots initiatives (85), and socio-economic settings, such as transition economies or post conflict economies (93). In these studies, context is identified as a key driver of lifestyle but individuals respond differently according to their worldviews, values, perceptions and attitudes.

Box 2. Definitions of Low-Carbon (Green, Sustainable, Pro-Environmental) Lifestyles & Lifestyle Change.

Definitions emphasising purpose and intentional

- “rethinking our ways of living, what we buy and how we organise our everyday lives ... altering how we socialise, exchange, share, educate and build identities” (94)
- “making changes to one’s lifestyle in order to reduce one’s carbon footprint through intentionally adopting new technologies and/or changing behaviour” (95)
- “something that needs to be changed to achieve sustainable development” (7)
- “consumers’ behaviours and choices if these are intentionally aimed at fulfilling sustainable development goals”(88)

Definitions emphasising impacts or outcomes

- “patterns of action and choices that are shaped by a group of factors capable of minimizing the wastage of natural resources, providing a better quality of life and do not jeopardize the needs of future generations” (96)
- “the changes that lead, or aim to lead, to the avoidance, shift and in some cases, improvement (depending on the context) in energy service demand, irrespective of their intent” (46)
- “shifts in the household demand for goods and services, mobility and housing choices” (97)

4.2 What are common elements of low-carbon lifestyles? How do these vary across domains?

Table 4 summarises evidence on the common behavioural, cognitive, and contextual elements of lifestyle in food, homes, and transport domains (see Appendices for further details on the underlying studies). Although the specific behaviours of interest necessarily vary by domain, the basic conceptualisation of lifestyle being constituted by three interacting elements is the same across domains, as are the types of cognitions and contextual factors considered relevant. Here we summarise some general insights as well as analytical emphases in food, homes and energy, and mobility-related lifestyles research.

Food-related lifestyles

Changes to eating habits and food choices are driven by individual attitudes, environmental awareness and intent (87). This cognitive approach relates a set of actions to a set of values e.g., (32) or intentional behaviours, driven by motivations, opportunities and habits (88). In developing or transitioning economies, a cognitive approach suggests that lifestyles shift as the goals of satisfying basic needs are replaced by goals of higher standards of living (93). However context as a strong lifestyle driver is emphasised in several food-related studies. At a global level, dietary choices and consumer purchases are driven almost entirely by cultural and socio-economic characteristics (28). Thøgersen (34) uses country of residence as an explanation for observed cross-national heterogeneity in food-related lifestyles within the EU.

Homes and energy-related lifestyles

Homes-related lifestyles in a domestic context are often narrowly concerned with direct and indirect uses of energy given its high relevance for carbon emissions. Energy-using

behaviours are the result of individual psychological variables that influence decision-making (e.g., attitudes, perceptions, and beliefs) as well as and household characteristics (18). As in low-carbon research more generally, many studies take a cognitive approach in identifying housing or energy-related perceptions, beliefs, and choices (33, 98). For example, Barr and Gilg (4) explored sustainable lifestyles in and around the home by linking everyday energy-saving actions to attitudes, values and situational factors.

Mobility and transport-related lifestyles

Transport-related lifestyles in a low-carbon context are commonly concerned with mode choice, active modes, and EV purchasing. Access to infrastructure, and urban or built environments are more influential than in other domains (21). For example, Markvica, Millonig (27) defined lifestyle groups associated with active mobility (walking, cycling) on the basis of attitudes (e.g., to leisure and transport) and fundamental values within socio-economic structures (such as income, education, residential characteristics). Some transport-related studies also take a reflexive view of lifestyle as informing and conveying self-identity (40). For example, an individual may purchase an electric vehicle (EV) if this fits in with their current or aspirational self-concept as a pro-environmentalist or technological enthusiast.

Table 4. Lifestyle elements by domain, drawing on studies of domain-specific lifestyles and studies looking at general lifestyles across domains.

Domain (n studies)	Behaviours	Cognitions	Contexts
Food & diet (8)	<p>Sustainable dietary choices: e.g., vegetarian diet, low nutritional value foods, highly processed foods, seasonal / local foods.</p> <p>Food waste prevention: use food waste as fertiliser or for composting.</p> <p>Sufficiency: e.g., benchmark 2424 calories per day / calorie intake.</p> <p>Self-sufficiency: growing own food.</p>	<p>Values and perceptions: e.g., food as necessity, luxury)</p> <p>Attitudes: environmental awareness, frugality, moral questioning of the excesses of consumption.</p> <p>Motives and goals: for food purchases, including quality, intentions for environmentally friendly food purchases, and anticipated consequences.</p> <p>Self-efficacy: control diet or food choices.</p>	<p>Economy: financial resources, economic crisis</p> <p>Political conditions: policy measures and regulation, conflict.</p> <p>Social: informal social networks or social structures, social norms regarding food choices, social values.</p> <p>Culture and traditions.</p> <p>Media: food advertising</p> <p>Country of residence as a broad contextual factor.</p> <p>Geo-physical conditions.</p>
Housing (4) and Energy (9)	<p>Housing: repair or renovate using environmentally friendly materials.</p> <p>Choice of energy supplier: renewables.</p> <p>Reduce energy consumption: for space heating / cooling, water heating, appliance use.</p> <p>Use of energy-saving devices: light bulbs, thermostat, insulation.</p> <p>Home energy generation: e.g., solar panels</p>	<p>Knowledge: e.g., awareness of energy ratings for appliances.</p> <p>Valued qualities of the home: amenities, size of house, home-maker, bathing preferences, living standards.</p> <p>Beliefs & attitudes: environmental and climate issues, new technology such as smart meters / customer innovativeness.</p>	<p>Economic: cost of electrical appliances, financial resources for installation of energy saving / generating equipment.</p> <p>Social: sense of community, social identity, community micro-gen, social trends e.g., eco-upgrading is not fashionable.</p> <p>Regulatory: installation of energy saving devices in social housing, energy</p>

	Residence: ecovillage, shared housing.	Perceptions: thermal comfort, logistics – ease and ability of taking action. Motivations: willingness to conserve energy. Responsibility for action: (individual, local authority, government), powerlessness.	labelling of electrical appliances. Physical environment: size of dwelling, climate, infrastructure, access to energy saving devices.
Transport & mobility (13)	Reduce vehicle ownership and use. Reduce air travel. Shift to public transport instead of car use. Shift to active transport: cycling or walking. Car-sharing. Purchase electric vehicle. Work from home to reduce vehicle use, video-conferencing to reduce air travel.	Knowledge: awareness of the association between transport use and emissions. Beliefs & values: biospheric, altruistic, egoistic and traditional. Attitudes: Willingness to act, openness, concern about the environment, transport mode opinions, openness. Motivations: e.g., for EV use – environment, or interest in technology, cost savings. Perceptions: e.g., public transport is inconvenient. Self-identity: family orientation, pro-environmental activities, career, hobbies & interests, sense of power.	Socioeconomic factors: income, education. Social: sociocultural norms, social interactions, socio-demographic variables. Regulation and policies: e.g., government subsidies for purchasing an electric vehicle, investment in cycling facilities. Physical environment: infrastructure (e.g., density of cycling networks), access to EV recharge facilities.

4.3 What frameworks are used to measure low-carbon lifestyles?

Analytical frameworks in low-carbon research align with the patterned, cognitive and reflexive views of lifestyle set out earlier in this report (Table 5). All three views recognise the interrelationships between behaviours, cognitions, and contexts, but with different emphases.

Analysis taking a patterned view of lifestyles is structured around behavioural matrices in specific domains (e.g., home energy, transport, food and diet). In some studies lifestyles are identified solely on the basis of activity patterns to then explore the association between lifestyle and attitudes or contextual factors (4, 21, 28, 85). More often, the patterned approach explicitly considers context or situational factors in the identification of lifestyles such as household characteristics (18), and local infrastructure and available mobility options (27). Studies also exploit variation in context to assess the influence of contextual factors on lifestyle, as in studies of urban-rural differences in home energy use in China (99) and in Beijing (47).

From a cognitive perspective, analytical frameworks emphasise the role of certain cognitions such as altruistic values and awareness of environmental problems associated with climate change to motivate and direct behaviours. From this perspective, lifestyles are purposeful but also responsive to contextual factors ranging from living and consumption situations (35) to socio-economic factors such as levels of education and income (87), and physical and social structures (100). Thøgersen (34) constructs domain-specific lifestyle

frameworks for food, housing, and travel. For example, the food-related lifestyle (FRL) framework measures five interacting lifestyle elements: two cognitive elements related to purchasing motives and food quality; two behavioural elements related to purchasing and preparing; and one contextual element related to the sites of food consumption (34).

A reflexive approach to low-carbon lifestyles emphasises the ways in which behaviours are used to express and reinforce self-identity. Blending behavioural patterns with motives and intentions, the constituent elements of lifestyle are broadly the same as in the patterned and cognitive approaches, but there is a greater emphasis on differentiation through social status and symbols of identity (40, 101). For example, Binder and Blankenberg (91) analysed UK household panel data to assess the degree to which pro-environmental behaviours influence and are influenced by subjective wellbeing and self-image. In a contrasting qualitative study of the lifestyles of 'home-front transitioners' in Sweden, Hagbert and Bradley (102) developed narrative themes with residents as agents of change in developing self-sufficient lifestyles. Axsen, Cairns (40) also use narrative themes which inform and reflect self-identity to explore pioneers' adoption of electric vehicles.

4.4 What data and methods are used in low-carbon lifestyles research?

A variety of quantitative and qualitative methods are used to identify and measure low-carbon lifestyles (Table 5). Quantitative methods collect data on lifestyle elements through questionnaire surveys (43) or other secondary datasets e.g., (90). Data reduction methods are commonly applied prior to analysis of lifestyle heterogeneity e.g., (4, 21). For example, composite lifestyle elements can be identified using factor analysis (92), principal component analysis (33, 34) or multiple correspondence analysis (93). Lifestyles defined by motivational homogeneity are also framed through rudimentary categorisation, such as members or non-members of environmental groups (103).

Qualitative approaches gather information through in-depth interviews or focus groups to develop narrative themes appropriate to sustainable lifestyles in general or 'voluntary simplicity' (104). Motivational narratives are developed for context-specific lifestyles, such as social housing tenants in Belfast (98), or engagement in community sustainability projects (105). Howell (95) used mixed methods (in-depth interviews and questionnaires) to explore values and motivations as routes to engagement in low-carbon lifestyles case studies. Hagbert and Bradley (102) used in-depth interviews to identify an emerging theme of 'home as a node of everyday life' as a starting point for low-carbon lifestyles. Residents were viewed as agents of change and alternative conceptualisations were explored for more radical forms of low-carbon living. This reflexive approach is also used in domain-specific lifestyle studies, such as understanding the motives for electric vehicle purchase (40, 101, 106).

Mixed methods approaches combine qualitative focus groups and in-depth interviews, with quantitative surveys (5, 27, 96). Vita, Lundström (85) for example, used backcasting workshops to develop narratives of low-carbon consumption narratives.

Low-carbon lifestyles research is concentrated in environmentally-conscious population segments in the global North. Available studies in emerging economies tend to place less emphasis on intentions, and more emphasis on demographic, social or institutional factors

which shape emissions-intensive lifestyles such as migration from countryside to cities (47) or literacy, theft and corruption (96).

Table 5. Analytical frameworks, data & methods used in low-carbon lifestyles research.

Lifestyle approach	Framework, data, methods	Lifestyle variables	Lifestyle domains (References)
Patterned view: lifestyle as inter-related behaviours	Factor analysis of questionnaire items	Behaviours or habits	Multi-domain (4); Active mobility (107)
	Published surveys to develop lifestyle scenarios	Behaviours, situations	Multi-domain (43)
	Consumer Lifestyle Approach (CLA), National energy balance tables	Behaviours	Multi-domain, urban/rural (47, 99)
	Consumer Lifestyle Approach (CLA), Published survey data;	Behaviours, household characteristics	Multi-domain (18)
	Quantitative categorisation	Behaviour, GDP	Multi-domain, transitioning economies (108)
	Ecological footprints for cross-national data	Household consumption	Multi-domain (28)
	Mixed methods: survey data and stakeholder evidence	Behaviours	Multi-domain (90)
	Mixed methods: focus groups and survey	habits, options, local infrastructure, attitudes	Active mobility (27)
	Mixed methods: qualitative Interview and Questionnaire	Resource use, urban migration, socio-cultural factors, GDP.	Energy use, Transitioning economies (96)
	Mixed methods: Focus groups, in-depth interviews, questionnaire	Behaviours (home – journey – holiday settings)	Multi-domain Context-specific (5)
	Qualitative: narratives from backcasting workshops	Participant visions of consumption patterns	Multi-domain (85)
Cognitive view: lifestyles as values, goals and intentions	Factor analysis of survey items	Attitudes, awareness, beliefs	General lifestyle Context specific: Transition economy (92)
	Principal component analysis of survey items	Actions, perceptions, values, motives, living & consumption situations	Domain specific (separate for housing, food and transport) (33, 35)
	Multiple correspondence analysis - survey items. Frame: response to economic crisis	Practices (consumption & digital), values & attitudes	Context-specific: economic crisis (93)
	Questionnaire (web-based); environmental policy instruments.	Behaviours, habits, awareness, intention, education, income.	Generalised lifestyle (87)
	Standardised questionnaire for carbon footprints,	Behaviours, self-satisfaction (wellbeing), living standards	Multi-domain Context specific: members / non-members of environmental groups (85)
	Quantitative: published surveys, lifestyle scenarios around coherent hypothesis	Consumption, attitudes, preferences, demography, income	Multi-domain (97)
	Qualitative: focus groups – thematic analysis approach	Practices, knowledge, identity, values, perceptions, motivation, structural context.	Generalised – sustainable lifestyle (100)
	Qualitative: in-depth interviews	Values, awareness, attitudes, perceptions	Generalised simplifier lifestyles (104)
Qualitative: semi-structured Interviews; Frame: perception of responsibility	Behaviours, environmental responsibility, willingness	Multi-domain Context specific – social housing tenants (98).	

	Qualitative; in-depth interviews Frame: motives and interactions:	Engagement history, involvement, project type, motives	Context specific s: community sustainability project (105)
	Mixed methods: in-depth interviews & questionnaire	Values e.g., altruistic, biospheric, egotistic	General low-carbon lifestyle (95)
Reflexive view: lifestyles as self- and social identity	Quantitative, Household Longitudinal Study Self-identified lifestyle group by questionnaire	Behaviours, subjective self-image / wellbeing,	General lifestyle (91)
	Cluster analysis or composite score of survey items	Activities (environment or technological), liminality, environmental concern	Domain specific: Transport (Plug in EV) (101, 106)
	Qualitative: Narratives themes from in-depth interviews	Practices, perceptions, motivations, home characterisation.	General lifestyle 'home front transitioners' (102)
	Qualitative: semi-structured interviews – identify themes	Practices, social interactions that shape identify	Domain specific: Transport (EV) (40)

4.5 How is lifestyle heterogeneity characterised in low-carbon research? What lifestyle groups are identified?

Lifestyle groups in low-carbon studies are identified and characterised using a variety of techniques. Quantitative techniques include cluster analysis (4, 5, 27, 92, 93, 106), latent class analysis (33-35, 87), evidence-based expert opinion (90, 96), lifestyle scenarios based on a set of coherent hypotheses (97), categorisation based on a single lifestyle factor like perceptions of responsibility (98), and self-identified lifestyles (91). Qualitative techniques can also be used to develop evidence-based lifestyle typologies (105) or narrative themes (40, 102, 104).

Based on the 30 empirical studies reviewed (see Appendices for details), lifestyle groups of individuals or households at the population level can be characterised in five broad ways, based on their:

1. Pro-environmental action
2. Basic orientation
3. Perceptions of self and world
4. Consistency across domains
5. Contextual drivers

Pro-environmental action

Lifestyle groups differentiated by level of engagement with pro-environmental behaviours represent an action scale from most to least committed (4, 5, 91). Although behaviours are the focus of group identification, heterogeneity is associated with other cognitive and contextual factors such as social cohesion (4), perceived lack of time (92), and other contextual constraints. Middlemiss (105) identified engagement typologies linked to motivation which in some groups highlight the gap between intent and action. Barr, Shaw (5) note that segmenting populations on the basis of pro-environmental behaviour is problematic without also taking into account inconsistencies across sites of action (see below for further discussion of inconsistency).

Basic orientation

Lifestyle groups can be defined by basic orientations or preferences towards a range of needs, actions and values ranging from environment and technology (101), communication needs and information (27), family or career (34), or leisure activities such as 'active outdoors' or 'beach-oriented' groups (21). Basic orientation lifestyle groups tend to be domain-specific, identified using a variety of techniques such as cluster analysis and narrative themes combining behaviours with cognitions. Differing motivations and attitudes towards self-image, efficiency, or social connections and responsibilities are reflected in disparate preferences. These basic orientation-defined lifestyle groups are useful for targeting intervention strategies or tailored information to particularly receptive sub-populations.

Perceptions of self and world

Perceptions of self and the world are cognitions which direct actions in a coherent sense across domains, and can form the basis of distinct lifestyle groups. Inward-looking cognitions include self-satisfaction and wellbeing, whereas outward-looking cognitions include community resilience and reducing environmental damage. For example, Hayles and Dean (98) distinguish 'active' from 'passive' lifestyle groups (willingness to take individual responsibility vs. environmental action is others' responsibility). Focusing on alternative sustainability lifestyles, Hagbert and Bradley (102) developed narrative themes that were either more outward-looking ('building local resilience') or inward-looking ('self-sufficiency' through food production). These lifestyle groups were sensitive to contextual factors that variously constrained or widened lifestyle choices.

Consistency across domains

Internal consistency across behaviours, cognitions and contexts form the basis of lifestyle groups applicable in a general sense across multiple domains. Such studies use observational evidence (93) or a coherent set of prior expectations (43, 97). The important cognitions identified tend not to be related to basic orientations or particular preferences but relate to more generalised responses to situational factors (93), or a coherent assimilation of preferences and attitudes within multiple settings such as home, work and society (97).

Contextual drivers

Context-driven lifestyle groups emphasise actions or consumption patterns embedded in social and physical environments. Such studies use both local case studies and national assessments. One case study in Nigeria found key contextual drivers to be socio-cultural, including corruption, levels of literacy, and demography (96). In a global assessment of consumption lifestyles structured around a one-planet, two-planet, three-planet WWF framework (28), the key contextual drivers of differing lifestyle groups were identified as being urban structure, culture, and socio-economic characteristics. Within countries, differing income and development patterns in rural and urban environments also drive weaker or stronger trends in consumption patterns between lifestyle groups (47). Large social and economic differences can set some societies apart from others, but collective responses to contextual factors are also differentiated by attitudes (93).

4.6 How consistent are low-carbon lifestyles?

The basic conceptualisation of lifestyle suggests consistency between its constituent elements (behaviours, cognitions, contexts). However there are many potential inconsistencies in low-carbon lifestyles between actions on the one hand, and cognitions and contextual factors on the other.

First, the 'knowledge-action' gap makes clear that awareness of environmental damage and potential responses does not necessarily lead to action (2). Longo, Shankar (109) suggest that too much knowledge can become a source of dilemma that produces tensions and paralysis.

Second, the 'value-action' gap extends this inconsistency to inconsistencies between values, goals, intent, and sustainable behaviours (105). Binder and Blankenberg (91) distinguish between perceived lifestyle (e.g., green self-image) and actual lifestyle (e.g., actual pro-environmental behaviours).

Third, lifestyle practices such as recycling may be inconsistent when observed across different sites of practices, e.g., at home and on holiday (5). From a reflexive view, consistency of pro-environmental behaviours across contexts is related to environmental self-identity: 'I am therefore I do' (110). However, contextual constraints such as reduced availability of recycling bins in workplaces and holiday destinations can lead to inconsistency across domains (111).

4.7 What is low-carbon lifestyle change? How is it promoted?

"Green lifestyle change is a gradual, deliberate process that is a response to environmental harms. Thinking of going green as adopting a lifestyle creates a relatively coherent story and collective vision of the future ... it encourages changes in everyday practices so individuals may live out the environmental themes they use to make sense of their actions" (37).

In low-carbon research, lifestyle change involves a shift in everyday activities to reduce consumption or resource use (87, 112) or to transition towards more sustainable practices (100). As the opening quotation suggests, low-carbon lifestyle change tends to be framed through a cognitive view of lifestyles which implies individual responsibility (103). But lifestyle change can also be viewed reflexively if changes in behaviour fit self-identity aspirations or allow individuals to differentiate themselves from others in society (42). However, as noted in earlier discussions of inconsistency, intention to change may not always translate into action.

Low-carbon lifestyle change can also be driven by enabling or constraining contextual factors. For example, collective grassroots initiatives provide a supportive context to foster pro-environmental attitudes and habits across multiple domains. Conversely, structural factors such as resource access or information inadequacies may act as a widespread barrier to lifestyle change. The balance between cognitions and contextual factors as drivers of lifestyle change differs across lifestyle groups. For example, a lower use of resources may not arise out of environmental consciousness but out of financial need or motivations linked to social justice.

Interventions range from short-term targeted campaigns to educate and inform (7, 95, 100, 113) to longer-term and more radical shifts in infrastructure, regulatory measures and social structures (43, 97, 113). Interventions can be 'traditional' or 'alternative' (114). Traditional approaches frame lifestyle change as a process through which an individual becomes increasingly willing to act. Interventions to promote low-carbon lifestyle change therefore seek to motivate self-determined action and responsibility towards the environment (see Appendices for details of studies reviewed). Interventions aim to change perceptions, beliefs, desires, and strengthen intentions (7). Examples include campaigns to build awareness of the need to act (100), goal setting and feedback (113), targeted interventions for shifting values and attitudes (113) and behaviour-change campaigns to reduce energy and water use (98). Such approaches tend to be effective only with a minority subset of motivated individuals (113). They are also often focused on behavioural change rather than the much broader integrative notion of lifestyle change.

Alternative approaches include 'habit discontinuities', 'choice architecture', and 'systemic' interventions (114). Habit discontinuity refers to changing unconscious behaviours or routines when they are disrupted by changes in context such as house moves, job changes, or infrastructure changes (114). Such approaches are criticised for their lack of practicality. The concept of 'choice architecture' refers to interventions that nudge people into a particular course of action by managing the information and influences which make up their choice environment. Such approaches are difficult to scale up (114).

Systemic approaches emphasise the wider socio-cultural contexts within which behaviour change occurs (113). Examples of interventions include those which seek to create 'information bridges' between opinion leaders of low-carbon lifestyles with clusters or groups of individuals (88). This recognises that intentions towards lifestyle change are strengthened by influential others including close social networks, co-workers, local communities, like minded others, as well as wider social norms (7) and community action (95, 105). Systemic approaches can be applied at many levels including communities, businesses, nations, cultures or sub-cultures. They can also result in lasting behaviour change which is embedded in structures that encourage and support change (114). These systemic approaches emphasise that not all interventions rely on individual action, particularly if 'agency' or responsibility is enshrined in government, industry, or technological infrastructure (98).

5 Synthesis and Insights for Low-Carbon Lifestyles Research

In this final section, we look across the distinct fields of lifestyles research to draw out similarities, differences, generalisable themes, and insights to inform analytical work on low-carbon lifestyles. We have kept this final section as a series of discrete points to emphasise that these are an initial set of ideas, reflections, as well as analytical insights.

5.1 What are the similarities across different research fields on lifestyles?

- a) Behaviours, cognitions, context are the three main elements of lifestyles, i.e., lifestyles are constituted by the relationships between behaviours and cognitions in specific contexts.
- b) Lifestyles are observable through patterns of behaviour in multiple domains of everyday life such as diet, travel, domestic living, and physical activity.
- c) Contextual elements of lifestyle are both social (e.g., culture, inter-personal relationships) and material (e.g., urban form, housing stock, climate). Contextual influences on lifestyle are commonly proxied through socioeconomic variables such as age, gender, and income.
- d) Lifestyles are measured at the individual level and sometimes at the household level (which can then be clustered into groups at a population level). Lifestyles are highly heterogeneous within any given population.
- e) Cluster analysis, latent class analysis, and other grouping techniques are commonly used to identify behavioural lifestyle clusters in population-level data sets, often using nationally-representative questionnaire survey data.
- f) Lifestyles are measured and analysed in order to understand how they can be changed through targeted interventions or strategies to benefit either individuals or society as a whole.
- g) Motivation and ability to change lifestyle is constrained in practice by available socioeconomic resources (e.g., disposable income, social relationships) and contextual factors (e.g., social norms, access to infrastructure).
- h) Empirical work on lifestyles is concentrated in the global North, with available studies in emerging economies placing more emphasis on demographic and institutional factors which determine lifestyles rather than values and goals as cognitive elements of lifestyle.

5.2 What are the differences between different research fields on lifestyles?

- a) Public health research is focused on a narrow and fixed set of lifestyle elements (diet, physical activity, smoking and drinking), *whereas* marketing and low-carbon research are concerned with a broad and variable set of lifestyle elements.
- b) Public health and marketing research tend to find or assume consistency in lifestyles *whereas* low-carbon research points to the possible inconsistencies between behaviours and cognitions (e.g., knowledge-action gap, value-action gap) or between domains.
- c) Public health research uses the terminology of 'risk factors' associated with 'worse' outcomes (unhealthy lifestyles, morbidity, mortality), *whereas* marketing and environmental research use more neutral terminology recognising either personal or social outcomes.

- d) Public health and low-carbon research make normative assumptions about ‘better’ and ‘worse’ lifestyles (or ‘more’ and ‘less’ desirable lifestyles) defined against public policy objectives, *whereas* marketing research is agnostic towards the social desirability of different lifestyles.
- e) Public health research and marketing research are applied to promote lifestyle change towards ‘better’ outcomes for the individual (personal health, material wellbeing), *whereas* low-carbon research is applied to promote lifestyle change towards ‘better’ outcomes for society (which may involve a loss of personal wellbeing). However, integrative frameworks for promoting health and sustainability lifestyles are eroding this distinction.
- f) Public health and low-carbon research place more emphasis on motivated reasoning for lifestyle change and so lifestyle elements such as values, problem awareness, self-efficacy and social norms, *whereas* marketing research places more emphasis on identity and social positioning, as well as private benefits of lifestyle change.
- g) Public health research and marketing research use lifestyle as a unifying, integrative concept across different domains of everyday life, *whereas* environmental research also sees lifestyle as domain-specific, as in ‘energy-related lifestyle’ or ‘travel-related lifestyle’.

5.3 How can frameworks and lifestyle elements from public health and marketing inform research on low-carbon lifestyles?

- a) Cognitions associated with a healthy lifestyle include both knowledge and awareness of health-related risk factors and morbidity outcomes, but also include broader cognitions such as purpose in life, emotional resilience, feeling at peace, managing stress, self-efficacy, strong social relationships, and mindfulness. These broader cognitions are useful for broadening out low-carbon lifestyles research beyond a narrow focus on specific behavioural changes (e.g., less flying, less red meat).
- b) In public health research there is a tendency for lifestyle practices associated with poor health outcomes to cluster. For example those with a healthy diet tend not to smoke and be more physically active, whereas those with unhealthy diets tend to smoke and drink more and be less physically active. This emphasises the importance of individual cognitions such as self-efficacy and knowledge, as well as physical and social environments, in shaping lifestyle-related behaviours. It is less clear in low-carbon research whether ‘good’ and ‘bad’ behaviours are as consistently clustered, or whether there is more evidence of inconsistency between behaviours under similar cognitive and contextual conditions. This should be explored more systematically in available behavioural data sets.
- c) Public health research emphasises well-being outcomes of lifestyles. Well-being could also serve as a useful foundational concept in low-carbon lifestyle research, in linking both to living standards and welfare, but also to self-identity and self-consistency with deeply-held values. Well-being concepts make salient that low-carbon lifestyle change will not simply be driven by motivated reasoning about the collective desirability of emission reductions, but also by the positioning of low-carbon lifestyles within people’s understanding and awareness of what constitutes a good or desirable life.
- d) Public health research has traditionally focused narrowly on health-related risk factors and related behaviours (diet, physical activity). However a wider understanding of public health to include personal development, livelihoods, social relationships, and so on,

provide a broader set of connections between healthy and low-carbon lifestyles. The Lifestyle of Health and Sustainability (LOHAS) framework in public health is an example of the increasing recognition that health and environmental sustainability are strongly intertwined.

5.4 How can the use of data and analytical techniques in public health and marketing inform work on low-carbon lifestyles?

- a) Empirical work in public health to characterise lifestyle heterogeneity and develop targeted interventions draws on a wide range of data including behavioural, psychological, contextual, sociodemographic, and clinical indicators or variables. Low-carbon lifestyle research can be narrowly concerned with behaviours, but this lacks the necessary cognitive and contextual information to understand lifestyles as an integrative concept distinct from behaviour.
- b) Given the strong relationships between public health and environmental sustainability, data resources that are widely used and with a long track record in monitoring health-related lifestyles could be useful for low-carbon research. As an example, the UK BioBank has extensive health and well-being data on half a million people tracking different age cohorts over time. So far it has been extensively mined to identify lifestyles associated with poor health outcomes, but this analysis could extend to poor environmental outcomes also.
- c) National statistical agencies in some countries have panel data sets for tracking lifestyle change with respect to health outcomes. For example, the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS) collects data through their Public Health Outcomes Framework which has been running since 1982 and is also spatially disaggregated. These types of national statistical data sets would lend themselves to comparative cross-country lifestyle-related analysis in a low-carbon context.
- d) Analyses of health-related behavioural clusters in population-level data sets are typically linked to socioeconomic and other observable contextual factors which are readily measured. Linking national-level behavioural heterogeneity to cognitions is less common, presumably due to data constraints. This is a similar limitation in low-carbon research which should explore opportunities to link datasets measuring relevant cognitions.
- e) The World Values Survey measures people's values and beliefs across almost 100 countries, using items from the widely-used Schwartz scale for assessing value systems. This aligns with the value systems approach used in marketing for identifying change over time and cross-cultural variation in lifestyles. This provides an available data resource for tracking the cognitive dimension to lifestyles at a global scale.
- f) The widely-used AIO framework in marketing distinguishes attitudes, interests, and opinions. This is a simple framework for identifying lifestyle heterogeneity. Applied to low-carbon research it emphasises that both what people do as well as how concerned they are about climate change help define lifestyle in a general sense across domains. For example, a simple 2x2 application would be to use an activity dimension and a concern dimension, and map lifestyle groups in the high/high, low/low, high/low, low/high domains. Following precedent in marketing, this could be implemented using a multi-item survey at the population level across countries, with cluster analysis then used to identify unique lifestyle groups.

5.5 How can insights on lifestyle change and interventions in public health and marketing inform work on low-carbon lifestyles?

- a) Public health research identifies risk factors associated with unhealthy lifestyles which are undesirable for both private reasons (morbidity, reduced quality of life) and public reasons (cost to health system). Similar language could be applied to high-carbon lifestyles to emphasise private and public undesirability. For example, frequent flyer membership and urban SUV ownership are 'risk factors' associated with high-carbon lifestyles. This may help increase the legitimacy of risk-mitigating public policy interventions promoting lifestyle change to reduce collective risks from climate change.
- b) Public health research recognises broad societal factors like deprivation which shape and constrain lifestyles alongside intentions and other cognitions. Design and evaluation of low-carbon interventions should more strongly recognise the limits to intention-driven lifestyle change.
- c) Public health interventions target specific lifestyle-related behaviours such as more regular physical exercise or better calorie controlled nutrient rich diets, but focus on a broad set of related cognitions and contextual factors. Interventions to promote low-carbon lifestyles tend to dilute the clear causal relationships between the intervention to change relevant cognitions or contextual factors, and the behavioural outcomes desired.
- d) Lifestyle change approaches in public health, as well as associated theoretical frameworks for health interventions, strongly emphasise the importance of cognitions such as knowledge, self-efficacy, and awareness of barriers to change. This means that lifestyle change interventions tend to be strongly inter-personal with relatively low sample sizes of participants, and strong interaction with public health professionals. A similar approach in low-carbon lifestyle change would target and work directly with 'at risk' groups of high-emitters in specific contexts. However, the willingness or openness of such groups may be limited as the personal benefits of such change will be unclear or even negative (e.g., frequent flyers).
- e) Apps are increasingly used in public health interventions to support self-monitoring and users' sense of control and self-efficacy. Similar approaches may be possible in low-carbon interventions allowing users to track carbon footprints across different domains of consumption and activity.
- f) Targeting of lifestyle interventions towards families and/or young people in social settings helps embed healthy practices and awareness at early stages, as well as the social reinforcement supportive of enduring lifestyle change. Similar approaches are possible for low-carbon lifestyle interventions.
- g) Although public health interventions tend to focus on specific at-risk population segments, policies to promote healthy lifestyles clearly recognise the importance of available infrastructure (e.g., access to exercise facilities) and economic incentives and information (e.g., advertising of unhealthy products, relative pricing of healthy and unhealthy alternatives). Low-carbon lifestyle change interventions need to take a similarly comprehensive approach, combining multiple strategies tailored to specific circumstances. What are recognised as 'lifestyle-change interventions' in climate policy explicitly exclude economic measures such as carbon taxes, and tend to focus more narrowly on normative and educational approaches to shape cognitions.
- h) Standardised scales for measuring voluntary simplicity in marketing date back to the 1980s, yet now correspond with a renewed interest in 'sufficiency' within sustainable

consumption research.

5.6 What have we learnt from this synthesis of lifestyles research for advancing the analysis and modelling of low-carbon lifestyles?

This report synthesised insights from conceptual and empirical studies of lifestyle in public health, marketing, and low-carbon research. Only a few modelling studies were included within the sample of 82 studies reviewed and annotated (summarised in Box 3). This concluding section sets out some initial ideas for developing this research field based on the body of lifestyles research reviewed.

Box 3. Snapshot of the current state-of-the-art with global scenarios and modelling of low-carbon lifestyles.

Low-carbon lifestyles are incorporated into global modelling analysis of climate mitigation through scenario narratives which are mapped into changes in energy demand or changes in certain activities in mobility, housing, or food (112).

Scenario narratives describe major shifts in the longer-term lifestyle landscape including changes in normative values (from individualism to collectivism) (97), increasing consumer dependence on the digital economy (43, 97), increasing urbanisation and virtualisation of society (43), or widespread 'green' values motivating low-carbon lifestyle change (112).

One current research challenge is if and how to shift implementation approaches from exogenous representation of lifestyle change in scenario narratives to endogenous generation of lifestyle change dynamics within models (46). Another research challenge is to develop generalisable frameworks for identifying archetypal lifestyle groups which can be consistently implemented in global models.

- a) Lifestyle change in global modelling to-date has been implemented as a fairly arbitrary set of behavioural changes (within an existing technological and infrastructural context) motivated by normative awareness of climate change described in scenario narratives. More robust scenario narratives should recognise lifestyle heterogeneity (within and between countries), as well as inconsistencies between intentions and actions.
- b) Lifestyle concepts describe sets of behaviours and cognitions across multiple domains in which contextual factors vary. However a highly granular representation of lifestyles is neither possible nor desirable in global models. A small number of lifestyle archetypes or generalisable groups are necessary to ensure modelling is tractable. Historical data on consumption activity which tracks both change over time and differences between countries would help inform future-oriented implementations of lifestyle concepts.
- c) Market research companies have established approaches for measuring lifestyle groups at national and cross-national scales. For example, the Sinus-Milieu approach distinguishes lifestyle groups along two dimensions (social status and degree of modernisation) to identify 10 lifestyle groups. Their latest database has 300,000 quantitative responses from people all over the world. Although powerful, and at a consistent scale to inform global modelling, access to market research methods and data is proprietary (and so costly). Some groups (e.g., the MUSE model led by Adam Hawkes at Imperial College, London) have integrated Sinus-Milieu classifications into their modelling.
- d) Market research companies have 'catchy' classifications for distinguishing lifestyle

groups. As an example, Rope-Consumer-Styles distinguishes dreamers, adventurers, open-minded, homebodies, rational-realists, organics, settled, and demanding. These describe lifestyle aspirations and values which would fit well with scenario narratives. As a contrasting example, MOSAIC distinguishes city prosperity, country living, rural reality, senior security, suburban stability, domestic success, aspiring homemakers, among other lifestyle groups. These describe basic sociodemographic and contextual lifestyles which would fit well with endogenous model representations.

- e) Frameworks which distinguish lifestyle groups based on degrees of innovativeness and receptiveness to social influences (e.g., VALS2) align with theories of diffusion and social learning which have already been tested in global IAMs. Similar approaches to developing a generalisable set of lifestyle archetypes could provide a way to model a wider range of lifestyle interventions, from 'traditional' interventions which act on cognitions, to 'systemic' interventions which act on material infrastructures.

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